

Integrating Mathematical Data and Resources: Advancements in zbMATH Open for Enhanced Mathematical Research Accessibility and Reproducibility

Maxence Azzouz-Thuderoz¹[0000-0002-8710-9548], Madhurima
Deb¹[0000-0001-5988-5366], Matteo Petrera¹, Moritz
Schubotz¹[0000-0001-7141-4997], and Olaf Teschke¹[0009-0003-4089-9647]

Department of Mathematics, FIZ Karlsruhe, Berlin, Germany

Abstract. We report the ongoing efforts of swMATH, an integral part of zbMATH Open, to collect precise referencing software metadata. zbMATH Open is emerging as a unified platform offering a spectrum of mathematical resources, including mathematical software, formulas, reviews, and serial and mathematical item classification. zbMATH Open offers connection to external partners, DLMF and OEIS, via its Links API by indexing approximately 6,330 documents containing 65,069 references to OEIS sequences and 15,858 references to 2,053 DLMF functions. Significantly, the collection of 44,594 software entries from swMATH is entirely accessible through zbMATH Open. Here, we emphasize the accurate referencing of mathematical software in swMATH for maintaining integrity, advancing mathematical research, and enhancing reproducibility. We describe how swMATH is embedded into zbMATH open and elaborate on the relationship of software and other mathematical research data like OEIS and DLMF, ensuring a complete and FAIR resource for the mathematical research community.

Keywords: zbMATH Open · software · metadata

1 The swMATH journey

1.1 On the importance of metadata for software

Software is taking a growing specific place in research [6]. They are actionable knowledge and often part of the scientific knowledge process. For this, they are unavoidable when one needs to ensure that scientific work is reproducible. Years ago, the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) [21] movement hit the rock of science. The FAIR principles [14] stated for research data have been extended to research software to improve the sustainability of research software. Especially, the authors state that *metadata, data, and software should be well-described such that they can be reused, combined, and extended in different settings.*

As an illustration of the importance of FAIR research data, [5] provides a list of mathematical object registries like the *Database of Ring Theory*, *MathRepo*, or *The House of Graphs* and sets their degree of compliance with the FAIR principles. However, like any STEM discipline, mathematics has also been concerned with the importance of mathematics software sustainability. Specifically, [7] suggested a methodology to build metadata to improve the FAIRness of mathematics software. Furthermore, other mathematicians have developed software, such as [15], that implemented models in topology, with the first goal being reusability.

1.2 swMATH as an extension of zbMATH Open

zbMATH Open is today the world's largest portal for mathematics research information services. Originating in Germany in 1868 as a mathematical review service, the entity later rebranded as Zentralblatt MATH, has evolved into the premier destination for accessing scientific articles in mathematics since its inception in 2021.

Complementing zbMATH Open, the swMATH database service was introduced in 2013 to bolster the discoverability and prominence of research software within the mathematics community [13]. By late 2023, this resource had been seamlessly integrated into and become accessible through the zbMATH Open interface [1]. Scholars now benefit from a consolidated interface on the zbMATH Open website, where they can comprehensively access information about mathematical software. This integration streamlines the research process, enhancing accessibility and efficiency for the global mathematical community.

The zbMATH Open interface integrates a collection of interlinked metadata entities as authors, articles, and software, all in-house indexed, forming a collection of persistent identifiers (PIDs) distinct and autonomous from any third-party dependant identifiers such as DOIs or ORCIDs. These mathematics domain-based PIDs are connected to formulas and numbers from registries like OEIS and DLMF and are categorized according to the Mathematics Subject Classification [10]. All these items form a world-class, rich knowledge graph of academic mathematical outputs.

These metadata often support hyperlinks to publications like DOIs and arXiv preprint papers. Lastly, citing mathematics articles in a BibTeX format is facilitated by a dedicated button on the zbMATH Open platform.

Moreover, zbMATH launched in 2021 an Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) service to make zbMATH an open and interoperable resource [19]. OAI-PMH is a computer protocol developed by the Open Archives Initiative to exchange metadata. It enables the creation and automatic updating of centralized repositories where metadata from various sources can be queried simultaneously. It leaves the possibility of read-only access to resources. Additionally, the zbMATH Open Links API is widely usable in tracing biblio-

graphic references related to a specific topic under the present partners of zbMATH Open, DLMF and OEIS. This API enables researchers to access DLMF [3] or OEIS [11] objects cited at zbMATH Open. Furthermore, one can retrieve the links associated with a mathematical subject classification (MSC) code or author ID. 6,312 links from zbMATH Open to DLMF and 67,436 links from zbMATH Open to OEIS are displayed on the zbMATH Open website. This tool is essential for statistically analyzing the bibliographic content in DLMF or OEIS. Continuously to this work, a REST API service has also been released in 2023 [12], making for the first time swMATH metadata interoperable in a standard way.

In parallel, the German Mathematical Research Data Initiative (MaRDI) portal has also initiated an OAI-PMH service to display rich domain contents. We look forward to reporting further on our work connecting swMATH to the MaRDI portal, which caters to swMATH as a pioneer research software catalog.

2 swMATH in the EOSC

2.1 Protecting source code and indexing it, a fruitful collaboration with Software Heritage

The SIRS [4] report, unveiled in 2020, introduced the ARDC principles, shedding light on the inherent fragility of software and emphasizing the need to establish a robust scholarly infrastructure to ensure the longevity of research software. Aggregators like swMATH are urged to adhere to these principles, with the FAIRCORE4EOSC project striving to enforce FAIR compliance within software catalogs such as swMATH [21]. The authors delineate fundamental principles for software development in academic research, encompassing Archiving, Referencing, Describing, and Citing software. As swMATH serves as a catalog, it references software and its metadata but does not store the source code. This limitation raises concerns about the accessibility and longevity of software hosted on various servers or platforms. Consequently, zbMATH Open may encounter the common issue of link rot, where URL links to software projects become inaccessible over time. To address these challenges, swMATH has partnered with Software Heritage to enhance its ARDC compliance [2]. In 2018, Software Heritage was established as a long-term software preservation library to archive all open-source software projects worldwide. With over 200 million archived projects from platforms like GitHub and BitBucket, Software Heritage plays a crucial role in the FAIRCORE4EOSC project as a universal archive for scientific software repositories. Furthermore, Software Heritage has developed the SWHID [9], an intrinsic persistent identifier for software, facilitating the identification of software projects and their versions. As shown in Figure 1, more than 13,000 of the 39,749 swMATH software [20] used standard repository services like GitHub or GitLab for development. The source code of these repositories has been archived and indexed thanks to the set of APIs supported by Software Heritage [17]. These archive source codes are accessible from the zbMATH Open interface with user-friendly URLs [20].

Table 1. Overview of the identified repository services in swMATH

	Number of swMATH software
No identified repository service	27,942
GitHub	16,373
GitLab	226
Bitbucket	91

By implementing these principles, swMATH aims to solidify its position as a dependable software catalog within the EOSC ecosystem.

2.2 Disseminating software metadata for the advancement of Open Science

In recent years, software metadata has garnered significant attention within the scholarly community [16]. Recognized as indispensable components for comprehending the functionality and purpose of software, they are essential to guarantee the reproducibility of scientific results. Scholars create and utilize software metadata, but also aggregators like swMATH which are able to carry out information regarding the impact of the software, like software citations in articles or related software projects. While the source code forms the software’s core, it alone often proves insufficient for fully grasping the intricacies of its functionality. Emphasizing the importance of robust metadata retrieval is paramount to understanding the impact of software in a specific scientific domain. To facilitate the discovery and utilization of software metadata, platforms such as swMATH require broader dissemination to reach a wider audience. By enhancing the visibility and accessibility of this highest-order scientific output, swMATH can significantly improve the discoverability and utilization of software resources within the academic community.

2.3 swMATH: Towards a connected resource into the EOSC ecosystem

Since June 2022, the Department of Mathematics at FIZ Karlsruhe has actively participated in the European Open Science Cloud Program through its involvement in the FAIRCORE4EOSC project. This initiative is dedicated to advancing the adherence to FAIR principles within digital research outputs, aiming to develop nine core components. Leveraging the zbMATH Open portal and the swMATH catalog, we strive to demonstrate how the implementation of these components enhances the FAIRness of the zbMATH Open portal while also fostering synergies with the MaRDI portal, the German national initiative for mathematics:

- EOSC Research Discovery Graph (RDGraph)
- PID Graph

- EOSC Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR)
- EOSC Data Type Registry (DTR)
- EOSC PID Meta Resolver
- EOSC Research Activity Identifier Service (RAiD)
- EOSC Research Software APIs and Connectors (RSAC)

Fig. 1. The workflow to connect swMATH into the EOSC

Through its involvement in the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, zbMATH Open is actively making its metadata accessible to the scientific community, as shown in Figure 2. The REST API deployed by FIZ Karlsruhe to showcase swMATH metadata serves as the foundation for our ongoing efforts to expose metadata in a standardized manner. This API is an invaluable tool for efficiently populating the OAI-PMH server, which is supported and instantiated by the MaRDI infrastructure. The adoption of the OAI-PMH protocol has emerged as a gold standard among Open Science institutions for managing scholarly archives. Notably, the MaRDI infrastructure is intended to integrate seamlessly into the EOSC ecosystem, contributing directly to the infrastructure of the PIDGraph. As a compliant OAI-PMH service endorsed by DataCite, the PIDGraph facilitates the enhanced interconnection of swMATH metadata with other scholarly entities. Preliminary findings [18] suggest that numerous mappings between entities within the PIDGraph and zbMATH can be further anticipated, resulting in enriched entity linking within the domain-specific knowledge graph of mathematics. Moreover, the RDGraph, a scientific knowledge graph supported by OpenAIRE, aggregates metadata from the PIDGraph, further enhancing the accessibility and discoverability of scholarly resources. In parallel to swMATH, a similar workflow is developed to process the zbMATH article’s metadata.

2.4 swMATH adopted CodeMeta as the standard format to display software metadata

Beyond its core initiatives, zbMATH Open enhances its software infrastructure by implementing appropriate metadata standards such as CodeMeta or DataCite. CodeMeta, a recognized standard vocabulary for software metadata, facilitates the comprehensive description of our software through rich metadata. This encompasses critical details such as authorship, versioning, citations from scholarly articles referencing the software, and publications announcing new releases. By embracing these standards, we aim to enhance the accessibility and comprehensibility of our software offerings, fostering greater transparency and collaboration within the academic community. The metadata will be accessible

@context	https://doi.org/10.5063/schema/codemeta-2.0
@type	SoftwareSourceCode
license	https://spdx.org/licenses/GPL-2.0-or-later
codeRepository	https://github.com/sagemath/sage
dateCreated	2005-02-24
datePublished	2005-02-24
dateModified	2023-09-16
issueTracker	https://github.com/sagemath/sage/issues
name	SageMath
version	10.2.beta3
description	<i>Sage (SageMath) is free, open-source math software that supports research and teaching in algebra, geometry, number theory, cryptography, numerical computation, and related areas. Both the Sage development model and the technology in Sage itself are distinguished by an extremely strong emphasis on openness, community, cooperation, and collaboration: we are building the car, not reinventing the wheel. The overall goal of Sage is to create a viable, free, open-source alternative to Maple, Mathematica, Magma, and MATLAB. Computer algebra system (CAS).</i>
applicationCategory	Mathematics
developmentStatus	active
relatedLink	https://epubs.siam.org/doi/book/10.1137/1.9781611975468
programmingLanguage	Python, Cython, C, C++, Lisp, Fortran
operatingSystem	macOS, Windows(WSL), Linux,
softwareRequirements	For detailed informations visit the download link on the SageMath Website, https://doc.sagemath.org/html/en/installation/index.html#

Fig. 2. The metadata of the SageMath software exposed into the CodeMeta vocabulary

and downloadable through a MediaWiki instance supported by the MaRDI infrastructure, providing essential information for convenient software citation. To facilitate this process, swMATH will present citable versions of this metadata in BibLaTeX format. BibLaTeX, widely utilized for citation management in LaTeX documents, has recently seen enhancements with dedicated software entries [8]. We anticipate integrating BibLaTeX utilities into the MediaWiki interface and the zbMATH Open portal, enabling one-click correction of research software citations in LaTeX documents.

3 Conclusion

We showcased the crucial role played by software metadata as a critical hidden pillar of scientific research. swMATH, by becoming an even more connected resource in the open science landscape, is intended to be a reliable resource for mathematicians, discretely advancing mathematics research. More than ever, the interconnection of software source code, metadata, articles, authors, formulae, and other digital mathematics entities is necessary to encompass a scientific knowledge production natively compatible with the FAIR criteria. From that, we look forward to improving research software citations by giving mathematicians the credit they deserve. Future work will also consider the possibility of better associating source code and related metadata.

Acknowledgements

This research is supported by the FAIRCORE4EOSC (Core Components Supporting a FAIR EOSC) project, funded by the EU’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101057264 and Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) under Grant Agreement No. 460135501, NFDI, 29/1 “MaRDI - Mathematische Forschungsdateninitiative”.

References

- [1] Maxence Azzouz-Thuderoz, Moritz Schubotz, and Olaf Teschke. “Sustaining the swMATH project: Integration into zbMATH Open interface and Open Data perspectives”. In: *European Mathematical Society Magazine* 126 (Dec. 14, 2022), pp. 62–64. ISSN: 2747-7894, 2747-7908. DOI: 10.4171/mag/118.
- [2] Michelle Barker et al. “Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software”. In: *Scientific Data* 9.1 (Oct. 14, 2022), p. 622. ISSN: 2052-4463. DOI: 10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x.
- [3] Howard S. Cohl, Olaf Teschke, and Moritz Schubotz. “Connecting Islands: Bridging zbMATH and DLMF with Scholix, a blueprint for connecting expert knowledge systems”. In: *European Mathematical Society Magazine* 120 (July 2021), pp. 66–67. ISSN: 2747-7894, 2747-7908. DOI: 10.4171/mag/35.
- [4] European Commission, Directorate-General for Research, and Innovation. *Scholarly infrastructures for research software – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Group (WG) Architecture Task Force (TF) SIRS*. Publications Office, 2020. DOI: doi/10.2777/28598.
- [5] Tim Conrad et al. *Making Mathematical Research Data FAIR: A Technology Overview*. Sept. 21, 2023. arXiv: 2309.11829[cs].
- [6] David De Roure et al. *UK Research Software Survey 2014*. 2014.
- [7] Antony Della Vecchia, Michael Joswig, and Benjamin Lorenz. *A FAIR File Format for Mathematical Software*. Sept. 1, 2023. arXiv: 2309.00465[cs].

- [8] Roberto Di Cosmo. “Announcing biblatex-software: software citation made easy”. In: *SIGSOFT Softw. Eng. Notes* 45.4 (Oct. 2020). Place: New York, NY, USA Publisher: Association for Computing Machinery, pp. 22–23. ISSN: 0163-5948. DOI: 10.1145/3417564.3417570.
- [9] Roberto Di Cosmo. “Archiving and Referencing Source Code with Software Heritage”. In: *Mathematical Software – ICMS 2020*. Ed. by Anna Maria Bigatti et al. Vol. 12097. Series Title: Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2020, pp. 362–373. ISBN: 978-3-030-52200-1. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-52200-1_36.
- [10] Edward Dunne and Klaus Hulek. “Mathematics Subject Classification 2020”. In: *EMS Newsletter* 2020-3.115 (Mar. 3, 2020), pp. 5–6. ISSN: 1027-488X. DOI: 10.4171/NEWS/115/2.
- [11] Dariush Ehsani, Matteo Petrera, and Olaf Teschke. “The integration of OEIS links in zbMATH Open”. In: *European Mathematical Society Magazine* 128 (Apr. 24, 2023), pp. 60–64. ISSN: 2747-7894, 2747-7908. DOI: 10.4171/mag/132.
- [12] Marcel Fuhrmann and Fabian Müller. “A REST API for zbMATH Open access”. In: *European Mathematical Society Magazine* (Dec. 2023), pp. 63–65. DOI: 10.4171/mag/174.
- [13] Gert-Martin Greuel and Wolfram Sperber. “swMATH – An Information Service for Mathematical Software”. In: *Mathematical Software – ICMS 2014*. Ed. by Hoon Hong and Chee Yap. Vol. 8592. Series Title: Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2014, pp. 691–701. ISBN: 978-3-662-44199-2. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-662-44199-2_103.
- [14] Wilhelm Hasselbring et al. “From FAIR research data toward FAIR and open research software”. In: *it - Information Technology* 62.1 (Feb. 25, 2020), pp. 39–47. ISSN: 2196-7032, 1611-2776. DOI: 10.1515/itit-2019-0040.
- [15] Carolina M. Jauregui et al. “Avoiding reinventing the wheel: reusable open-source topology optimization software”. In: *Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization* 66.6 (June 2023), p. 145. ISSN: 1615-147X, 1615-1488. DOI: 10.1007/s00158-023-03589-7.
- [16] Rafael C. Jiménez et al. “Four simple recommendations to encourage best practices in research software”. In: *F1000Research* 6 (June 13, 2017), p. 876. ISSN: 2046-1402. DOI: 10.12688/f1000research.11407.1.
- [17] Moritz Schubotz and Maxence Azzouz-Thuderoz. “Mapping of swMATH ids and Software Heritage ids”. In: (). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10854038.
- [18] Moritz Schubotz and Olaf Teschke. *Mapping between zbMATH Open identifiers, DOIs and ORCIDs*. Version v0.0.1. Nov. 29, 2022. DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.7378860.
- [19] Moritz Schubotz and Olaf Teschke. “zbMATH Open: Towards standardized machine interfaces to expose bibliographic metadata”. In: *European Mathematical Society Magazine* 119 (June 14, 2021), pp. 50–53. ISSN: 2747-7894, 2747-7908. DOI: 10.4171/mag/12.

- [20] [SW] The NFDI Consortium of Mathematics, *swMATH and FairCore4Eosc*. SWHID: `<swh:1:dir:1f5cb3e391f05844f2c67b4db70ab12bfb5467a9>`.
- [21] Mark D. Wilkinson et al. “The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship”. In: *Scientific Data* 3.1 (Mar. 15, 2016), p. 160018. ISSN: 2052-4463. DOI: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18.

Glossary

ARDC	Archive, Reference, Describe, Cite.
DLMF	Digital Library of Mathematical Functions.
DOI	Digital Object Identifier.
DOI	Scholarly Infrastructure for Research Software.
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud.
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable.
FAIRCORE4EOSC	Core Components Supporting a FAIR EOSC.
MaRDI	Mathematical Research Data Initiative.
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting.
OEIS	On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences.
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID.
PID	Persistent identifier.
PIDGraph	Persistent Identifier Graph.
REST API	Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface.
swMATH	swMATH is a catalog of mathematical software.
zbMATH Open	zbMATH Open (formerly known as Zentralblatt MATH) is a portal for the mathematics.